

Anticancer Agents : Part III. Synthesis of Substituted 2-(4-Methyl/Phenyl-1-Piperaziny)-Propanes.

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A number of substituted 2-(4-methyl/phenyl-1-piperaziny)-propane derivatives have been synthesised from 1-aryloxy-or thioaryloxy-2:3 epoxy propanes by condensation with a secondary amine, conversion of the product to the chloro derivative followed by treatment with 1-substituted piperazine. Some of the byproducts formed during the condensation of epichlorohydrin with phenols have been characterised. Pharmacology of these compounds are under study.

IN a programme to study the structure activity relationship of 1, 2, 3-substituted propane as anticancer agents, synthesis of some piperazine derivatives have previously been described^{1,2}. As an extension of the work we like to report here the synthesis of further new 1-morpholino-2-(4-methyl/phenyl-1-piperaziny) derivatives (Ia-Ib).

In view of the well known physiological activity of ephedrine it was also thought desirable to synthesise some piperazine compounds incorporating the ephedrine moiety in the molecule. Hence another new group of compounds 1-ephedrino-2(4 methyl/phenyl-1-piperaziny)-3-substituted Propanes (IIa-IId) have been synthesised.

The compounds were synthesised by condensation of 1-substituted piperazines with substituted 2-chloropropanes according to the general procedure described earlier¹. Thus the condensation of a phenol with epichlorohydrin to form 1-aryloxy-2:3-epoxy propane³ was followed by conversion to 1-amino-3-aryloxy-2-propanols⁴ with a secondary amine (morpholine or ephedrine), the chloro derivative of which on reaction

with appropriate (1 substituted) piperazine derivative led to the desired product.

1-Ephedrino-2-(4 phenyl-1-piperaziny)-3-thiophenoxypropane (IIc) was obtained also by an alternative procedure^{5,6} involving the condensation of 1-ephedrino-2-chloro-3-thiophenoxypropane with diethanolamine, followed by treatment of the product with SOCl₂ and finally cyclisation with aniline in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃.

The compounds (1,2,3-substituted propane) thus synthesised are listed in Table I.

It is of interest to note that condensation of 2:4 dichlorophenol (1 mole) with epichlorohydrin (1 mole) in NaOH (1.5 mole) yielded besides the desired epoxy propane derivative (37%) a higher boiling fraction (b. p. above 200°/0.8 mm, 11%) which quickly solidified and on crystallisation from pet. ether afforded needles, m.p. 119°-20°, ν_{max} Nujol 3340 cm⁻¹ (-OH). Analytical data of the compound corresponds to the molecular formula C₁₅H₁₂O₃Cl₄ (M⁺380). The structure of the compound could be easily deduced as III from an analysis of its mass and NMR spectrum.

c. R = 2:4 - C₆H₃Cl₂
b. R = p-C₆H₄OMe

a. R = p-C₆H₄OMe, R' = Me, X = O
b. R = 4-naphthyl, R' = Ph, X = O
c. R = R' = Ph, X = O
d. R = R' = Ph, X = S

TABLE I
R-CH₂-CH-CH₂-R'

Sl. No.	R	R'	X	Crystallising solvent	m. p./b. p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. formula	Calc. (%)	Found (%)
1.	-OC ₆ H ₃ Cl ₂	morpholino	OH		130-35/0.2 mm	42	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₃ Cl ₂	C: 50.99 H: 5.6	C: 50.91 H: 5.92
2.	-OC ₆ H ₃ Cl ₂	morpholino	Cl		150/0.2 mm	90	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ NO ₂ Cl ₂ †	C: 48.10 H: 4.98	C: 47.75 H: 5.19
3.	-OC ₆ H ₃ Cl ₂	morpholino	4-methyl-1-piperazinyl	ether : ethanol	152-53*	50	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂ , HCl	C: 50.89 H: 6.64	C: 50.52 H: 6.44
4.	-OC ₆ H ₄ OMe	morpholino	OH		150/0.8 mm	76	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ NO ₄	C: 62.9 H: 7.93	C: 62.35 H: 8.23
5.	-OC ₆ H ₄ OMe	morpholino	Cl		140/0.4 mm	76	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ NO ₃ Cl	C: 58.63 H: 7.03	C: 58.21 H: 7.43
6.	-OC ₆ H ₄ OMe	morpholino	4-methyl-1-piperazinyl	ether : ethanol	139-40*	69	C ₁₉ H ₃₁ N ₃ O ₃ , HCl	C: 59.14 H: 8.36	C: 58.83 H: 8.58
7.	-OC ₆ H ₄ OMe	ephedrine	OH		138-40/0.4 mm	61	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ NO ₄	C: 69.54 H: 7.89	C: 69.13 H: 7.66
8.	-OC ₆ H ₄ OMe	ephedrine	Cl		156/0.6 mm	90	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ NO ₃ Cl	C: 66.01 H: 7.20	C: 65.56 H: 7.05
9.	-OC ₆ H ₄ OMe	ephedrine	4-phenyl-1-piperazinyl	ether : ethanol	230-32*(dec)	45	C ₃₀ H ₃₉ N ₃ O ₃ , HCl	C: 68.49 H: 7.67	C: 65.56 H: 7.81
10.	-OC ₆ H ₅	ephedrine	OH		130/0.3 mm	48	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ NO ₃	C: 72.35 H: 7.99	C: 7.17 H: 8.15
11.	-OC ₆ H ₅	ephedrine	Cl		145/0.2 mm	79	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ NO ₂ Cl	C: 68.34 H: 7.24	C: 68.22 H: 7.41
12.	-OC ₆ H ₅	ephedrine	4-methyl-1-piperazinyl	ether : methanol	204* (dec)	75	C ₂₄ H ₃₅ N ₃ O ₂ , HCl	C: 66.41 H: 8.36	C: 66.08 H: 8.28
13.	-OC ₁₀ H ₇	ephedrine	OH		156-60/0.4 mm	50	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ NO ₃ ‡	C: 75.59 H: 7.45	C: 75.32 H: 7.39
14.	-OC ₁₀ H ₇	ephedrine	Cl		—	90	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ NO ₂ Cl §	C: 71.95 H: 6.83	C: 71.42 H: 6.97
15.	-OC ₁₀ H ₇	ephedrine	4-phenyl-1-piperazinyl	ether : methanol	200* (dec)	60	C ₃₃ H ₃₉ N ₃ O ₂ , HCl	C: 72.56 H: 7.38	C: 72.31 H: 7.35
16.	-SC ₆ H ₅	ephedrine	OH		145/0.6 mm	57	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ NO ₂ S	C: 68.84 H: 7.60	C: 68.26 H: 7.77
17.	-SC ₆ H ₅	ephedrine	Cl		153/0.2 mm	84	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ NOCIS	C: 65.22 H: 6.91	C: 64.83 H: 7.16
18.	-SC ₆ H ₅	ephedrine	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂		138/0.4 mm	70	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ N ₂ OCl ₂ S	C: 60.65 H: 7.08	C: 60.42 H: 7.38
19.	-SC ₆ H ₅	ephedrine	4-phenyl-1-piperazinyl	ether : methanol	220-22*	61	C ₂₉ H ₃₇ N ₃ OS, 3HCl	C: 59.53 H: 6.89	C: 59.18 H: 7.11

*m. P. reported as its hydrochloride; †n_D²⁸ = 1.35; ‡n_D²⁸ = 1.38; §n_D²⁸ = 1.6; || n_D²⁵ = 1.45

III

a, m/e 145

b, m/e 175, R = CH₂

c, m/e 201, R = -CH=CH-CH₂

d, m/e 162, R = H

Thus the 60 MHz NMR spectrum showed characteristic signals at $\delta_{\text{CDCl}_3}^{\text{ppm}}$ 2.85 (1H, m, exchangeable with D_2O , >CH-OH); 4.25 (4H, d, $J=4$ Hz, $2 \times \text{-OCH}_2\text{-CH}$); 4.47 (1H, m, >CH-OH); 6.93 (2H, d, $J=9$ Hz, $6'\text{-H}$ & $6''\text{-H}$); 7.24 (2H, dd, $J=9$ Hz, 2Hz, $5'\text{-H}$ & $5''\text{-H}$); 7.4 (2H, d, $J=2$ Hz, $3'\text{-H}$ & $3''\text{-H}$).

The mass spectrum of the compound (III) showed the molecular ion peak at m/e 380 with significant $M+2$ and $M+4$ peaks due to the heavier chlorine isotope. In addition to the peaks at m/e 145, 175 and 201 assignable to species a, b, c respectively, the spectrum also showed intense peaks at m/e 162 (d) and 218 (e) possibly originating from the same fragmentation involving hydrogen transfer⁷.

On the other hand, the condensation of p-methoxy phenol with epichlorohydrin under similar condition yielded along with the usual 1:2-epoxy-3-(p-methoxy phenoxy) propane, another compound in a poor yield (1%), m. p. $101^\circ\text{-}2^\circ$, mol. formula, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ 198), $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ $3310\text{-}3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (bonded OH), $\delta_{\text{CDCl}_3}^{\text{ppm}}$ 3.47 (2H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , $2 \times \text{-OH}$); 3.75 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 3.88 (5H, m, aliphatic protons), 6.83 (4H, s, Ar-H).

The mass spectrum of the compound showed besides the strong molecular ion, fragments at m/e 180 ($M^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 167 ($M^+ - \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$), 149 ($M^+ - \text{CH}_2\text{OH} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and 137 ($M^+ - \text{CHOHCH}_2\text{OH}$). An intense peak at m/e 124 could be assigned to the p-methoxy phenol ion. The fragmentation pattern led to the structure (IV) for the compound which is also in consonance with its NMR spectrum.

Although formation of $\alpha\alpha'$ -diaryloxy propan-2-ol of the type (III) has already been reported^{8,9} in the condensation of epichlorohydrin with phenols, the 1:2 diols (IV) was not mentioned so far during this type of condensation.

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